

Reactivity of dichloro-(1,10-phenanthroline)gold(III) chloride towards sulfite in phen-phenH⁺ buffer medium

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Abstract : The reactivity of dichloro-(1,10-phenanthroline)gold(III) chloride towards sulfite has been studied spectrophotometrically in phen-phenH⁺ buffer medium in the temperature range of 288 K to 303 K. The reaction between [Au(phen)Cl₂]⁺ and HSO₃⁻ in phen-phenH⁺ buffer medium shows 1 : 1 stoichiometry. The reaction exhibits first order dependence on [{Au(phen)Cl₂}Cl] and less than unit order dependence on [HSO₃⁻]. Phenanthroline has a retarding effect on the reaction rate. The variation in H⁺ concentration did not affect the rate of the reaction significantly. The reaction obeys the following rate expression.

$$-\frac{d[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}]_t}{dt} = \frac{kK[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}]_t [\text{HSO}_3^-]}{[\text{phen}] + K[\text{HSO}_3^-]} \quad (1)$$

The pseudo-first order rate constant decreases with the increase in ionic strength, while the reaction rate increases with the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium. The reaction possibly involved a one step two electron transfer process to produce AuCl₂⁻ and SO₄²⁻ as the reaction products of the respective reactants. A probable mechanism in conformity with the experimental observations has been suggested. The thermodynamic and the activation parameters were calculated with respect to the equilibrium step and the slow step of the reaction mechanism respectively.

Keywords : Dichloro-(1,10-phenanthroline)gold(III) chloride, sulfite, phen-phenH⁺ buffer, kinetics and mechanism.

Introduction

The chemistry of gold is a promising field of research that emphasizes on oxidation reduction reaction mechanisms. The coordination numbers of gold are found to be two, four and six among which two and four are relatively more important for gold(I) and gold(III) respectively. Although the coordination number six is adopted by gold(II) but the hexacoordinated gold(II) species are highly susceptible to disproportionation. Most of the trivalent gold complexes are powerful oxidizing agents. The redox potential for the system, Au³⁺ + 2e = Au⁺, is about 1.29 volt¹ at 298 K. Gold(III) is known to form com-

plexes²⁻⁴ with anions like Cl⁻, NO₃⁻ and CN⁻ to give AuCl₄⁻, Au(NO₃)₄⁻ and Au(CN)₄⁻, respectively. On the other hand, different coordinated cationic complexes⁵⁻⁷ like [Au(phen)Cl₂]Cl, [AuCl₂Py₂]Cl, [Au(bipy)Cl₂]ClO₄ and [Au(bipy)Br₂]ClO₄ involving 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl have also been prepared. The standard redox potentials of gold(III) complexes are reported⁸ where the values of E⁰ are related to the different ligands attached to gold(III). A number of studies have been reported on the mechanism of oxidations of several inorganic reducing substrates like N₂H₅⁺⁹, NH₃OH⁺¹⁰, HNO₂¹¹, H₃PO₂¹², HAsO₂¹³, H₂SO₃¹⁴ and H₂O₂¹⁵ by AuCl₄⁻. The ki-

netics of the reduction of gold(III) by platinum(II) have also been studied^{16,17} in acid medium. The kinetics of oxidation of oxalate ion^{18,19}, ethylene diamine^{20,21}, other poly amines^{22,23} and malonate²⁴ by gold(III) have been reported in acidic solution. There are also reports on the oxidation of some reducing sugar and sugar phosphates²⁵, alkanols and aryl alcohols²⁶, α -hydroxy acids²⁷ and amino acids²⁸⁻³² by tetrachloroaurate(III) in NaOAc-AcOH buffer medium. Au^{III} as an oxidant is of interest since it may behave either as a one or two electron transfer reagent. It seems that there is no literature data till date involving the oxidation of either organic or inorganic reductants by cationic gold(III) complexes. The present report deals with the kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of sulfite ion by dichloro-(1,10-phenanthroline)gold(III) chloride in weakly acid medium (phen-phenH⁺ buffer; pH range 4 to 5). The complex is stable in phen-phenH⁺ buffer medium over the pH range 4–5. An attempt has also been made to compare the kinetic and thermodynamic parameters along with the mechanistic paths of the present reaction with those of the oxidation of sulfite ion by anionic gold(III) chloride complex.

Experimental

Materials :

A sodium sulfite (GR, E. Merck) stock solution was prepared from solid sodium sulfite and kept under nitrogen to prevent auto oxidation, as trace metal catalysed auto oxidation of sulfite is well known. Sodium sulfite solutions were standardized by using an excess of standard I₃⁻ solution followed by back titration with standard sodium thiosulfate. 1,10-Phenanthroline monohydrate (GR, E. Merck) was used as received. Acetonitrile of E. Merck was used after steam distillation (to get 100% pure acetonitrile).

The complex [Au(phen)Cl₂]Cl was prepared by a modified procedure, as mentioned in literature⁵. A boiling solution of 1,10-phenanthroline monohydrate (0.55 g) in water (40 ml) was added to the aqueous solution of chloroauric acid (0.90 g in 20 ml water) with stirring. The pale yellow precipitate of [Au(phen)Cl₂][AuCl₄] was first deposited which was dissolved during boiling for few minutes. Then it

was filtered and in the filtrate finely powdered ammonium chloride (15 g) was added and was stirred until all the ammonium chloride had dissolved. Cooling to room temperature the prepared orange compound was filtered off and washed with small amounts of ethanol followed by dry ether. Elemental analysis of the recrystallized product yielded the results : Found : Cl, 22.4; Au, 40.4. Calcd. for C₁₂H₈N₂Cl₃Au : Cl, 22.0; Au, 40.8%.

Instruments :

Absorbance and electronic spectra were recorded with a Shimadzu (160 PC) spectrophotometer using 1.0 cm quartz cells. Solution pH values ranged from 4 to 5 and were measured with an Elico pH analyzer (Model LI 612) before and after the reaction. The linearity of the electrode was established using pH 4, 7 and 9.2 buffers.

Kinetic measurements :

The experiments were carried out under the condition in which the sulfite concentration was in large excess to that of the oxidant. Kinetics were performed at 373 nm where the complex absorbed more (about ten times) than phenanthroline. The kinetics was monitored *in situ* in the kinetic mode of the instrument in the electrically controlled thermostatted cell housing (CPS-240A). The change in absorbance was automatically and continuously recorded. For faster reactions, sulfite solution contains salt or solvent if any (adjusted to desire pH) were directly injected into the spectrophotometer cell. The total phenanthroline concentration, C_{phen} = ([phen] + [phenH⁺]) was in the range 0.5–2.5 mmol dm⁻³ and acted as weak buffer. The temperature was controlled within the limit of ± 0.1 °C. For determination of the activation parameters four different temperatures ranging from 288–303 K were used. Generally 8–10 experimental points are used to investigate the reaction. Pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were obtained graphically from log *A* (*A* = absorbance) against 'time' plots. The rate of decrease of gold(III) was followed for at least 50% conversion of the initial gold(III). The rate constants were reproducible within $\pm 5\%$. The reproducibility of the kinetic data was some times better than $\pm 5\%$.

Stoichiometric measurements and product analysis :

The stoichiometry of the reaction was studied under different experimental conditions. The gold(III) complex was mixed with excess sulfite. The oxidation product, sulfate (SO_4^{2-}) was estimated³³ gravimetrically as barium sulfate (BaSO_4) after acidification with HClO_4 and removal of excess sulfite as SO_2 was done by bubbling with dinitrogen. The results are recorded in Table 1. The ratio $\Delta[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}]/\Delta[\text{HSO}_3^-]$ was found to be 1.04. The reaction may be represented stoichiometrically as follows :

The existence of sulfate³³ in the reaction mixture was confirmed by the immediate precipitation of BaSO_4 upon addition of BaCl_2 . This is contrary to the observation made earlier in the oxidation of sulfite by anionic gold(III) complex in acid medium (HCl) where sulfite is oxidized to give two different products SO_4^{2-} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_6^{2-}$. The formation of phenanthroline as one of the reaction products has been tested as follows. One drop of the test solution containing the substrate and oxidant is mixed in a micro test tube with a drop of solution of 1 g of $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot (\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ to give a reddish brown color which is stable to dilute mineral acids. The color is believed to be due to the production of the complex cation between Fe^{2+} and phenanthroline. Appropriate blank tests confirmed the generation of phen. A solution of Fe^{II} of concentration $0.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ was added immediately to the reaction mixture containing $[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}]$, $[\text{HSO}_3^-]$ of $0.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $3.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at constant pH and temperature of 4.5 and 298 K respectively. The solution was analyzed spectrophotometri-

cally at 515 nm. Other reactants and products did not show any significant absorbance at this wavelength. The result indicates that absorbance increases with increase in time which is due to the increase in $[\text{phen}]$. Under present conditions dithionate was not detected (absence of orange color of the test solution with the addition of saturated alcoholic solution of *p*-dinitrobenzene in presence of ammonium hydroxide) as a reaction product.

Results

Dependence of rate on $[\{\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2\}\text{Cl}]$, $[\text{HSO}_3^-]$ and $[\text{phen}]$:

The influence of $[\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ on the pseudo-first order rate constant was studied at different $[\{\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2\}\text{Cl}]$ in the region $(0.5-2.0) \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ but at constant $[\text{HSO}_3^-]$, $[\text{phen}]$, ionic strength, pH and temperature of $2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $16 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, 4.5 and 298 K, respectively. The observed pseudo-first order rate constant was found to be $(2.17 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (Table 2), which indicates that the order with respect to $[\{\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2\}\text{Cl}]$ is unity.

The oxidation reaction was also studied at four different temperatures (288 K, 293 K, 298 K and 303 K) with variation of $[\text{HSO}_3^-]$ from $(1-5) \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ keeping $[\{\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2\}\text{Cl}]$ ($5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), $[\text{phen}]$ ($2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), ionic strength ($16 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) and pH (4.5) constant (Table 3). The rate of oxidation increases with the increase in substrate concentrations (Table 3). A Lineweaver and Burk plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ against $1/[\text{HSO}_3^-]$ (Fig. 1) at each temperature produced straight line ($R^2 \sim 0.99$) with a positive slope and a positive intercept on the ordinate. Such type of plot indicated the formation of an intermediate complex^{34,35} between sulfite and $[\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ in a fast pre-equilibrium step.

Table 1. Stoichiometry of reduction of the $[\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ by sulfite

$10^3 [\text{Au}^{\text{III}}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	pH	$10^3 [\text{phen}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^3 [\text{HSO}_3^-]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^3 [\text{SO}_4^{2-}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$\Delta[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}]/$ $\Delta[\text{HSO}_3^-]$
0.5	4.0	2.0	5	0.47	1.06
1.0	4.2	4.0	10	1.04	0.96
1.0	4.5	4.0	15	0.98	1.02
1.0	5.0	4.0	20	0.91	1.10

Table 2. Effect of $[\{\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2\}\text{Cl}]$, $[\text{phen}]$, ionic Strength (μ) and pH on the rate of oxidation of sulfite by dichloro-(1,10-phenanthroline)gold(III) chloride at 298 K

$10^3 [\{\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2\}\text{Cl}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^3 [\text{HSO}_3^-]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^3 [\text{phen}]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^2 \mu$ (mol dm^{-3})	pH	$10^3 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1})
0.5	2.5	2.0	1.60	4.5	2.18
1.0	2.5	2.0	1.60	4.5	2.14
1.5	2.5	2.0	1.60	4.5	2.21
2.0	2.5	2.0	1.60	4.5	2.16
0.5	4.5	0.5	1.60	4.5	9.34
0.5	4.5	1.0	1.60	4.5	5.98
0.5	4.5	1.5	1.60	4.5	4.53
0.5	4.5	2.0	1.60	4.5	3.42
0.5	4.5	2.5	1.60	4.5	2.98
0.5	3.5	2.0	1.10	4.5	2.96
0.5	3.5	2.0	1.80	4.5	2.70
0.5	3.5	2.0	3.10	4.5	2.52
0.5	3.5	2.0	4.10	4.5	2.34
0.5	3.5	2.0	5.10	4.5	2.16
0.5	3.5	2.0	1.60	4.0	2.78
0.5	3.5	2.0	1.60	4.2	2.81
0.5	3.5	2.0	1.60	4.5	2.84
0.5	3.5	2.0	1.60	4.8	2.76
0.5	3.5	2.0	1.60	5.0	2.87

Fig. 1. Effect of variation of sulfite concentrations on the pseudo-first order rate constant at different temperatures. Plots of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[\text{HSO}_3^-]^{-1}$. $[\{\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2\}\text{Cl}] = 5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{phen}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 16 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and pH = 4.5.

The dependence of the reaction rate on the concentration of phenanthroline was studied by varying its concentration in the range $(5-25) \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ at constant $[\{\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2\}\text{Cl}]$, $[\text{HSO}_3^-]$, ionic strength, pH and temperature (Table 2). The dependence of $[\text{phen}]$ was also studied at three different concentrations of HSO_3^- ($2.5, 3.5$ and $4.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) at 298 K. The rate constant was found to decrease with increasing $[\text{phen}]$ (Table 2). The plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $[\text{phen}]$ (Fig. 2) at each $[\text{HSO}_3^-]$ produced a straight line with a positive slope and a positive intercept on the y-axis.

Dependence of rate on ionic strength, pH and dielectric constant :

The influence of ionic strength on the pseudo-first order rate constant was studied at constant $[\{\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2\}\text{Cl}]$, $[\text{HSO}_3^-]$, $[\text{phen}]$, pH and temperature of $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $3.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, 4.5 and 298 K, respectively. Ionic

Table 3. Variation of pseudo-first order rate constant with $[\text{HSO}_3^-]$ on the reduction of $[\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2]\text{Cl}$ by HSO_3^- at different temperatures. $[\{\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2\}\text{Cl}] = 5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{phen}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 16 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{pH} = 4.5$

Temp. (K)	$10^3 [\text{HSO}_3^-]$ (mol dm^{-3})	$10^4 k_{\text{obs}}$ (s^{-1})	$10^3 k$ (s^{-1})	$10^2 K$
288	1.00	-	11.0	13.3
	1.25	8.44		
	2.00	13.1		
	2.50	15.1		
	3.50	21.0		
	5.00	27.8		
293	1.00	8.06	14.8	11.5
	1.25	9.98		
	2.00	15.3		
	2.50	18.7		
	3.50	24.4		
	5.00	33.7		
298	1.00	8.83	20.1	9.39
	1.25	11.5		
	2.00	17.7		
	2.50	21.2		
	3.50	27.3		
	5.00	37.7		
303	1.00	9.98	27.4	7.76
	1.25	13.1		
	2.00	20.0		
	2.50	25.3		
	3.50	31.5		
	5.00	42.1		

strength was varied by the addition of NaClO_4 to the reaction mixture (Table 2). The pseudo-first order rate constant decreases with the increase in ionic strength. The plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $\mu^{1/2}$ is linear (Fig. 3) with slope-1.1 which indicates that the reaction takes place between ions of unlike charges.

The influence of pH on the rate of oxidation was studied in the pH range 4 to 5 by varying phen-phenH⁺ buffer while the concentration of the Au^{III}, HSO_3^- , phen, ionic strength and temperature were kept fixed at $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $3.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $16 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and 298 K, respectively. The observed pseudo-first order rate constants are given in Table 2. The results indicate that hydrogen ion has no significant effect on the reaction rate

Fig. 2. Effect of $[\text{phen}]$ on the rate of reaction at different $[\text{HSO}_3^-]$. Plots of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[\text{phen}]$. $[\{\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2\}\text{Cl}] = 5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 16 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\text{pH} = 4.5$ and $\text{temp} = 298 \text{ K}$.

Fig. 3. Effect of variation of ionic strength on the pseudo-first order rate constant. Plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $\mu^{1/2}$ at 298 K. $[\{\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2\}\text{Cl}] = 5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{HSO}_3^-] = 3.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{phen}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{pH} = 4.5$.

at constant ionic strength.

The effect of variation in dielectric constant of the medium was studied by varying the percentage of acetonitrile in the range 0–40% v/v. Each experiment was carried out at constant $[\text{HSO}_3^-]$, $[\{\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2\}\text{Cl}]$, $[\text{phen}]$, ionic strength, pH and

temperature of $3.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $16 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, 4.5 and 298 K, respectively. The reaction rate of the reduction of dichloro-(1,10-phenanthroline)gold(III) chloride by sulfite decreases with increase in the dielectric constant of the medium. The values of dielectric constant for various proportions of acetonitrile at 298 K are taken from the work of Moreau and Douheret³⁶. The plot of $\log k$ against $1/\epsilon$ (ϵ = dielectric constant) is linear as shown in Fig. 4. The result indicates that the reaction takes place between ions of opposite charges.

Fig. 4. Effect of variation of dielectric constant on the pseudo-first order rate constant. Plot of $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ versus $1/\epsilon$ at 298 K. $[\{\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2\}\text{Cl}] = 5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{HSO}_3^-] = 3.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{phen}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $\mu = 16 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{pH} = 4.5$.

Free radicals test :

The intervention of free radical in the reaction was investigated with the addition of 20% acrylonitrile scavenger to the reaction mixture ($[\{\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2\}\text{Cl}] = 5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{HSO}_3^-] = 3.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{phen}] = 2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ and $\text{pH} = 4.5$) in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen and the reaction mixture was allowed to stand for one hour. There was no formation of suspension or precipitate of polyacrylonitrile³⁷ during the reaction, indicating the absence of involvement of free radical intermediate in the reaction.

Discussion

Sulphurous acid exists in aqueous solution in equilibrium with sulfite and hydrogen sulfite.

The K_1 and K_2 values³⁸ at 298 K are 1.6×10^{-2} and 1.0×10^{-7} , respectively. Since the reaction was investigated in the 4.0–5.0 pH range, it is likely equilibrium (3) predominated in the present reaction. It is suggested that HSO_3^- is the species which reacts with gold(III).

The kinetic experiments were carried out immediately after dissolving the complex in aqueous medium, since on standing the complex for several hours in water, the solution turned acidic. This is possibly because $[\text{AuCl}_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})]^+$ dissociated to give $[\text{AuCl}_2(\text{OH})]$ and H^+ . There is also literature evidence⁵ to indicate that the gold(III) complex readily ionizes in water to give $[\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2]^+$ and Cl^- which has been ascribed to the much greater solvation energy associated with water than with the non aqueous solvents like nitrobenzene and acetone. The absence of $[\text{Cl}^-]$ on the rate was not significant indicating $[\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2]^+$ is the reacting species. The reaction may be explained by considering that a 1 : 1 intermediate complex is formed between $[\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2]^+$ and $[\text{HSO}_3^-]$ followed by the decomposition of the intermediate compound (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The rate expression may be deduced,

$$-\frac{1}{[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}]_t} \frac{d[\text{Au}^{\text{III}}]_t}{dt} = \frac{kK[\text{HSO}_3^-]}{[\text{phen}] + K[\text{HSO}_3^-]} \quad (5)$$

or,

$$\frac{1}{k_{\text{obs}}} = \frac{1}{k} + \frac{[\text{phen}]}{kK[\text{HSO}_3^-]} \quad (6)$$

The eq. (6) suggests a linear plot of $1/k_{\text{obs}}$ against $1/[\text{HSO}_3^-]$ having a positive slope and positive intercept and this has been corroborated by the experimental results at each temperature (Fig. 1). Consequently the reaction seems to occur through the formation of the complex followed by its decomposition^{33,39} to give the reaction products. The values of k (disproportionation constant) and K (equilibrium constant) for the reaction (Scheme 1) were calculated from the linear plots (Fig. 1) at each temperature and were recorded in Table 3. The results indicated that both the values of k and K were found to increase with increasing temperature. The change of enthalpy (ΔH^0) and the corresponding change of entropy (ΔS^0) associated with the equilibrium step were evaluated from the linear plot of $\log K$ against $1/T$ (Fig. 5). The enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) followed by entropy of

activation (ΔS^\ddagger) were obtained from the plot of $\log(k/T)$ versus $1/T$ (Fig. 6) using the theory of absolute rates. The values of ΔH^0 , ΔS^0 , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger are recorded in Table 4. Eq. (6) also accounts for the linear plot of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[\text{phen}]$ (Fig. 2) and the results indicate that rate of reaction decreased in presence of added phenanthroline. The values of k and K have been evaluated at three different substrate concentrations and the average values are 19.9×10^{-3} (s^{-1}) and 8.56×10^{-2} respectively at 298 K. The values are found to be very near to the respective k and K at 298 K obtained from the plot of k_{obs}^{-1} versus $[\text{HSO}_3^-]^{-1}$ (Fig. 1), which corroborates the above reaction mechanism and the rate law.

Electron transfer from the substrate to the gold(III) complex occurs through the formation of a transition state as mentioned below (Scheme 2) which subsequently decomposes to give SO_3 and gold(I) in one step two electron transfer process.

Fig. 5. Influence of temperature on the equilibrium constant. Plot $\log K$ versus $1/T$.

Fig. 6. Effect of variation of temperature on the disproportionation constant. Plot $\log(k/T)$ versus $1/T$.

Table 4. Thermodynamic values associated with equilibrium steps and activation parameters for the oxidation of sulfite by anionic and cationic complex of gold(III)

Gold(III) complex	ΔH^0 (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔS^0 ($\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$)	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔS^\ddagger ($\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$)	Ref.
$[\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2]^+$	-26.3	-108.0	42.0	-137.4	Present study
$[\text{AuCl}_4^-]$	-18.2	11.8	26.9	-202.6	14

Scheme 2

Gold(I) is known to form complex with sulfite. Since the reaction has been carried out in excess sulfite the possibility of the formation of gold(I)-sulfite complex does exist. However, the sulfite complex $\text{Na}_3[\text{Au}(\text{SO}_3)_2]^-$ is formed only by the reduction of $[\text{Au}(\text{SO}_3)_4]^{5-}$ by OH^- in alkaline medium. Since the reaction has been studied in acid medium ($\text{pH} < 5.0$) such a possibility that Au^{I} -sulfite is formed has been ignored. Again during the reaction between $[\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2]^+$ and HSO_3^- coordination sphere of positively charged gold(III) is altered due to the loss of phen. The gold(III)-sulfite complex which was formed earlier is decomposed to give AuCl_2^- and SO_4^{2-} . The reaction therefore takes place by inner sphere mechanism.

We have earlier studied the oxidation of SO_3^{2-} by AuCl_4^- in acid medium¹⁴ where the reaction had occurred through the intermediate formation of the complex between the reactants followed by the decomposition to give free radical^{14,40} and Au^{II} . The free radical further reacts with Au^{III} to give SO_4^{2-} and Au^{II} . The latter subsequently by reacting with SO_3^{2-} gives SO_4^{2-} and $\text{S}_2\text{O}_6^{2-}$. Thus two different oxidation products had been obtained unlike the present study where only SO_4^{2-} is formed. The kinetic rate expression and stoichiometry are also different from the oxidation of SO_3^{2-} by cationic gold(III) complex. The activation parameters of these two reactions as recorded in Table 4 are widely different. The results indicate that AuCl_4^- oxidation of the substrate is characterized by lower entropy of activation than the reaction with cationic complex of gold(III). This is to be expected since for reactions between ions of opposite charges there is generally an entropy increase passing from reactants to activated state complex, for ions of like charge there is an entropy decrease.

The observed 1 : 1 stoichiometry and orders with respect to each reactant, the increased rate of reaction with decrease in ionic strength and dielectric constant and the absence of polymerisation in the presence of acrylonitrile, corroborated the suggested rate law and the reaction steps.

Conclusion

The redox reaction between dichloro-(1,10-phenanthroline)gold(III) chloride and sulfite in phen-phen H^+ buffer medium takes place through two electron transfer process. Under the experimental conditions, H^+ ion has little effect on the reaction rate, whereas phen has an inhibiting effect. The reaction involves the formation of an intermediate complex between $[\text{Au}(\text{phen})\text{Cl}_2]^+$ and HSO_3^- followed by the decomposition of the complex to give AuCl_2^- and SO_4^{2-} as the reaction products.

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